

Compounds of Hexamethylenetetramine with certain Salts of Silver and other Metals and the Influence of Anionic Volume on the Capacity for Association by the Central Positive Atom.

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As the result of a long series of investigations on the nature of auxiliary valencies, Ephraim has obtained some very interesting and important results. It has been observed that the capacity of a cation to associate with neutral molecules increases with the atomic or molecular volume of the anions and so far, that under certain circumstances the usually characteristic co-ordination value of six is overstepped (Ephraim, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 644 ; 1919, 52, 957; 1920, 53, 548; 1921, 54, 873). This increased capacity of the cations to associate with neutral molecules like water and ammonia with the increase in volume of the anions has been attributed by Ephraim to the existence of holes or empty spaces in the crystal lattice when the anion and cation forming the compound possess essentially different molecular volumes. These holes are then filled up by the neutral molecules and the crystal is thereby stabilised. Well developed, highly symmetrical forms of crystals of salts rich in water of crystallisation are quoted as instances in support of the above view.

On the other hand, Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1918, 51, 706) found that in the ammoniacates of silver halides which in the maximum take up 3 molecules of ammonia per atom of silver, the relationship is reversed. The stability diminishes from chloride to iodide inspite of the iodide ions being larger than the chloride ion. Similar anomalous results have also been obtained in the case of silver salts such as chlorate, bromate, iodate, perchlorate, perbromate, periodate, permanganate, nitrite and nitrate. This anomaly has been explained by Ephraim assuming that the ammoniacal silver halides are polymerised compounds in which the ammonia is distributed partially between the cation and the anion. In order to make a close examination of the influence of the anionic volume upon the capacity of the silver ion to associate with neutral molecules, a number of compounds of

silver salts with the non-volatile neutral molecule hexamethylenetetramine have been prepared and studied. These form the subject matter of the present paper. The following compounds of hexamethylenetetramine with various silver salts have been prepared.

3AgCN , B ; 2AgCNO , B ; 2AgCNS , B ; AgClO_4 , B ; Ag_2CrO_4 , B ; $4\text{Ag}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, 5B, $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Ag_2MoO_4 , 2B, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Ag_2WO_4 , 2B, H_2O ; $2\text{Ag}_2\text{SO}_4$, 3B, $6\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $4\text{Ag}_2\text{SO}_4$, 5B, $13\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Ag_2ScO_4 , 2B, $12\text{H}_2\text{O}$; where $\text{B} = (\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$.

To this a number of others already described by previous workers may be added for the sake of comprehensive comparison :

AgF , B, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 4AgCl , B ; 3AgBr , B ; 2AgI , B : AgClO_3 , B, H_2O and $\text{Ag}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, B (Vannino and Sachs, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1913, 251, 290); 4AgBr , B (Schwartz, *Chem. Zeit.*, 14, 787); AgNO_3 , B (Delepine, *Compt. rend.*, 1894, 119, 1211); 3AgNO_3 , 2B (Pratesi, *Gazzetta*, 1884, 13, 437); where $\text{B} = (\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$.

In the case of the halides the capacity of silver for association diminishes from flourine to chlorine—an anomaly already observed by Ephraim in their corresponding ammonium compounds. In all other cases the general regularity is maintained, that is, the increase in the anionic volume is accompanied with the increased capacity of association of neutral molecules by the cation silver. So the results of Ephraim's investigations about the influence of anionic volume upon the capacity of cation to manifest auxiliary valencies are supported to a great extent by the nature of the hexamine compounds studied in the present paper. As for the anomaly in the case of the silver fluoride noted above, which runs parallel with the corresponding ammoniacate, an explanation similar to that suggested by Ephraim for the ammonicates can be accepted.

In order to study the influence of cationic volume upon its capacity for association with neutral molecules, two compounds of copper and cadmium cyanide have been prepared. Their formulae are given below along with that of silver cyanide for comparison :

3CuCN , 2B ; $3\text{Cd}(\text{CN})_2$, B ; 3AgCN , B.

Now as the silver and cadmium ions have almost the same volume, the composition of their hexamine compounds is similar.

On the other hand copper with a smaller atomic volume possesses a higher degree of associating power as is to be expected.

The cadmium compound is not strictly comparable with cuprous and silver compounds as in it cadmium is present as a divalent cation.

Again unlike sulphate and selenate, silver tellurate does not form any compound with hexamine. Though according to Ephraim's rule the associating power of the silver atom in silver tellurate should have been developed to the maximum extent. This is very likely due to the condensation and extreme insolubility of silver tellurate. Similar explanation holds good also in the case of borate, iodate, phosphate, arsenite and arsenate of silver which fail to associate with hexamine molecules. Most of the salts whose hexamine compounds are described in this paper are insoluble in water; so also are their hexamine compounds. Hence their method of preparation is based on the principle of substitution. That is, the salts are dissolved in strong ammonia solution when they form soluble ammoniacates, then the solution is treated with a strong solution of hexamine and the mixed solution is evaporated when the hexamine compound crystallises out with the loss of ammonia.

where X is an acidic radical and m , n and p are integral numbers.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Silver Cyanide and Hexamine.—Freshly precipitated silver cyanide was dissolved in dil. ammonia by warming. The solution was filtered to remove any suspended impurities and to this an excess of a concentrated hexamine solution was added. The solution was concentrated by evaporating on water-bath. The fine precipitate formed was filtered, washed with cold water and finally with absolute alcohol and dried in a vacuum over sulphuric acid.

For analysis a weighed quantity of the substance was decomposed by evaporating with dil. sulphuric acid on the water-bath till no smell of formaldehyde and hydrocyanic acid was perceived. The silver was then precipitated from the solution as silver chloride and estimated as usual. Nitrogen was estimated by combustion. (Found: Ag, 59.3, 59.3; N, 17.86. $3\text{AgCN}, (\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires Ag, 59.9; N, 18.0 per cent.)

It is a white crystalline silky substance insoluble in cold water. When warmed with water the filtrate gives test for hexamine indicating partial decomposition.

Silver Thiocyanate and Hexamine.—Freshly precipitated silver thiocyanate was dissolved in concentrated ammonia solution with the aid of a little heat. The solution was filtered and to this was added a concentrated solution of hexamine in excess. The solution was concentrated on water-bath and was then cooled when a white crystalline precipitate separated out. These crystals were collected and recrystallised from ammonia. The crystallised salt was filtered, washed and dried as in the previous case.

For analysis a weighed quantity of the substance was taken in a beaker and was covered with water. Then bromine water was added in excess. The sulphur was oxidised to sulphuric acid and silver changed into silver bromide. To the mixture was added about 10 c. c. of dilute nitric acid, and it was kept for sometime on the water-bath to remove the excess of bromine. The precipitated silver bromide was estimated in the usual way. Sulphur was estimated in the filtrate as BaSO_4 . (Found: Ag, 46.16, 46.3; S, 13.5; N, 17.3. 2AgCNS , $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires Ag, 45.8; N, 17.8, S, 13.5 per cent.)

Cuprous Cyanide and Hexamine.—The method of preparation is identical with those of the previous compounds.

A weighed quantity of the substance was taken and evaporated with dil. sulphuric acid till no smell of formaldehyde was perceived. To this was then added a concentrated solution of caustic soda and the whole kept on a boiling water-bath to dehydrate the copper oxide and at the same time to drive off all the ammonia formed from the hexamine by previous decomposition by the acid. The contents of the basin were cooled and the copper estimated as copper oxide. (Found: Cu, 35.0; N, 28.1. 3CuCN , $2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires Cu, 34.6; N, 28.16 per cent.)

It is a white crystalline substance insoluble in water.

Cadmium Cyanide and Hexamine.—Freshly precipitated cadmium cyanide was dissolved in slight excess of dil. ammonia and to this a large excess of concentrated hexamine solution was added. The solution was filtered and evaporated on water-bath. The precipitate contained sufficient ammonia as ammoniacal compound. The precipitate was filtered, washed and suspended in a concentrated solution of hexamine and digested on the water-bath till the last trace of

ammonia had been removed. The white crystalline substance was filtered, washed and dried as usual. (Found: Cd, 52·7, 52·6; N, 22·4. $3\text{Cd}(\text{CN})_2$, $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires Cd, 53·1; N, 22·1 per cent.).

Cadmium was estimated as sulphate by evaporating with sulphuric acid.

Silver Cyanate and Hexamine.—Freshly precipitated silver cyanate dissolved in the smallest quantity of concentrated ammonia solution was added to a concentrated solution of hexamine in excess. The solution was filtered and allowed to evaporate spontaneously at the ordinary temperature. The fine crystalline precipitate obtained was recrystallised from ammonia in the cold, filtered, washed and dried in the usual way. (Found: Ag, 49·4; N, 19·07. 2AgCNO , $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires Ag, 49·1; N, 19·09 per cent.).

Silver Chromate and Hexamine.—Freshly precipitated silver chromate was dissolved in slight excess of dilute ammonia. The solution was filtered and crystallised with the addition of excess of hexamine solution at a comparatively low temperature on the water-bath when beautiful yellow crystalline crust separated. This was filtered and recrystallised from ammonia solution. The crystals were filtered, washed and dried as usual.

The yellow compound was also obtained by digesting the dark red silver chromate with a solution of hexamine. (Found: Ag, 45·63; N, 12·1, 12·3; Cr, 11·27. Ag_2CrO_4 , $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires Ag, 45·7; Cr, 11·0; N, 11·8 per cent.).

Silver Dichromate and Hexamine.—The freshly precipitated silver dichromate was dissolved in nitric acid with the aid of a little heat. The content was cooled and filtered. A concentrated solution of hexamine was added to this solution drop by drop. The beautiful orange-red crystals formed were separated, washed and dried as usual. (Found: Ag, 34·8; Cr, 16·7, 16·6; N, 11·2. $4\text{Ag}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, $5(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 34·4; N, 11·2; Cr, 16·6 per cent.).

Silver Molybdate and Hexamine.—Freshly precipitated silver molybdate was dissolved in slight excess of concentrated ammonia. Then a concentrated solution of hexamine was added in excess. The solution was filtered and allowed to evaporate spontaneously in the dark when large, long, white shining crystals separated.

These were recrystallised from ammonia at the ordinary temperature and filtered, washed and dried in the usual way. (Found : Ag, 30·7 ; Mo, 13·66 ; N, 16·0. $\text{Ag}_2\text{MoO}_4, 2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 31·1 ; Mo, 13·8 ; N, 16·17 per cent.).

Silver Tungstate and Hexamine.—The preparation is exactly similar to that of the molybdate compound.

Tungsten was estimated as WO_3 by repeated evaporation with strong nitric acid. Silver was estimated in the filtrate from tungstic acid. (Found : Ag, 27·73, 27·8 ; W, 23·3 ; N, 14·2. $\text{Ag}_2\text{WO}_4, 2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 27·7 ; W, 23·57 ; N, 14·3 per cent.).

It is a white crystalline substance sparingly soluble in water. When boiled with water the substance is reduced ; when boiled with dil. nitric or sulphuric acid it is decomposed with the separation of tungstic acid accompanied by the liberation of formaldehyde.

Silver Sulphate and Hexamine.—(a) A solution of silver sulphate was gradually added to an excess of hexamine solution. The white crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed with a very dilute hexamine solution and finally with alcohol. It was then dried as usual. (Found : Ag, 37·9 ; N, 14·3. $2\text{Ag}_2\text{SO}_4, 3(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 37·5 ; N, 14·6 per cent.).

(b) On the other hand when a solution of hexamine was added to an excess of silver sulphate solution a different product was obtained. The substance was filtered, recrystallised from ammonia, washed with cold water and finally with alcohol and then dried as usual. (Found : Ag, 39·8, 40·0 ; N, 12·6. $4\text{Ag}_2\text{SO}_4, 5(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4, 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 39·6 ; N, 12·3 per cent.).

Silver Selenate and Hexamine.—The freshly precipitated silver selenate was dissolved in slight excess of ammonia. This was filtered and a concentrated solution of hexamine was added in excess. The solution was crystallised at ordinary temperature and the white crystals obtained were recrystallised from ammonia solution at room temperature. The crystals were finally washed and dried as usual. (Found : Ag, 25·4, 25·3 ; N, 13·15. $\text{Ag}_2\text{SeO}_4, 2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4, 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 25·2 ; N, 13·1 per cent.).

Silver Perchlorate and Hexamine.—A solution of perchloric acid was neutralised with freshly precipitated silver oxide by heating on water-bath. It was cooled filtered and to this a strong solution of

hexamine was gradually added. The white precipitate obtained was recrystallised from ammonia, filtered, washed, with cold water and finally with alcohol and dried in the usual way. (Found: Ag, 81·0, 81·3; N, 16·4. Ag ClO_4 , $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires Ag, 81·1; N, 16·1 per cent.).

General Properties of the Compounds.—All these substances are more or less easily soluble in ammonia solution. They are decomposed by mineral acids on warming with evolution of formaldehyde. Caustic alkalis decompose them with the formation of the metallic oxide. On being heated in a dry test tube they decompose with charring and emitting a fishy odour characteristic of amines.

A hexamine compound of cuproso-cupric cyanide of uncertain composition was obtained when cuprous cyanide was dissolved in concentrated ammonia and a current of air passed through it for several hours after the addition of hexamine solution. At first an ammonium compound of cupric cyanide separated then a brown precipitate began to be formed, when the liquid was filtered and more air passed through. The precipitate was a brown crystalline substance. It decomposes at ordinary temperature giving smell of cyanogen gas when kept for any length of time.

Silver benzoate gave a precipitate when evaporated spontaneously from ammoniacal solution to which hexamine was added in excess. The substance even after recrystallisation from ammonia did not give constant results.

Silver sulphite and silver salicylate behaved like the benzoate. They were all well-defined crystalline substances insoluble in water. The silver sulphite compound was found to be very unstable even at the ordinary temperature.

